

Studies on the Leaves of *Strychnos nuxvomica* Linn*

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Vomicine, the major alkaloid of the leaves of *Strychnos nuxvomica* gives positive Gibbs reaction, thereby adducing a direct evidence for the presence of a phenolic hydroxyl group, the proton of which is exchangeable with deuterium only when warmed with D_2O . The phenolic hydroxyl group is obstinate to methylation and acetylation. Even on prolonged treatment with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate it does not form any O-methyl ether.

Although the work on *Strychnos nuxvomica* L. started as early as 1819, much impetus for further investigation of this plant was received when Woodward and Brehm² correctly elucidated the structure of strychnine, the major alkaloid of the seeds of this botanical species.

The isolation and structure elaboration of curare alkaloids having strychnine moiety from various *Strychnos* species^{3,4,5,6} interested the present investigators to examine the leaves of *S. nuxvomica*. Recently Karrer and his co-workers⁷ have observed the presence of C-mavacurine, $C_{20}H_{25}ON_2^+$ (I) in the rootbark of the same plant. This has prompted the authors to report the results of their investigation on the leaves of *Strychnos nuxvomica*.

The petrol (b.p. 60-80°) extract of the leaves of *S. nuxvomica* showed three distinct alkaloid spots on TLC (R_f 0.08, 0.57 and 0.63). The least polar alkaloid is found to be identical with strychnine. The alkaloid having R_f value 0.57 is vomioine and the alkaloid (R_f 0.63) is under investigation. The major component of the strongly basic fraction of *S. nuxvomica* is vomioins (II), the spectral and chemical studies of which, not reported earlier, constitute the subject matter of the present paper.

Vomicine (yield, 0.1%), $C_{22}H_{24}N_2O_4$ (M^+ 380), crystallises from methanol in fine needles, m.p. 271-73° (dec.), $[\alpha]^{25}_D +86^\circ$ in $CHCl_3$, R_f 0.57 (adsorbent, silica gel-G, solvent: methanol, indicator: ceric ammonium sulphate) and 0.88 (adsorbent: silica gel-G,

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solvent: chloroform: acetone: diethylamine: 5:4:1, indicator: ferric ammonium sulphate).

The colour reactions of the alkaloid are indicative of the presence of an indoline chromophore. The alkaloid shows absorption maxima in the U.V. region, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ m μ (log ϵ): 227 (4.29), 260 (4.03); 298 (3.64) which also suggest the dihydro indole nature of the compound. Though there was no shift in the U.V. spectrum in alkaline solution, in acid solution there was a slight change (hump at 220 m μ , besides the peaks at 260 and 298 m μ).

FIG. 1

The I.R. absorption spectrum of the base shows the presence of a bonded -OH (3.10 μ); C=O (6.01 μ); hydrogen bonded amide (6.18, 6.37 μ ,^B and an ether linkage (9.00 μ).

FIG. 2

The hydroxyl group indicated by the I.R. spectrum band at (3.10 μ) did not form any characteristic derivative even under drastic conditions. It, however, gives a positive Gibbs' test, thereby proving the presence of a phenolic hydroxyl, the para position of which is free. Although the alkaloid contains a phenolic hydroxyl it is insoluble in alkali, fails to undergo methylation with diazomethane in methanol and dimethyl formamide and acylation with the relevant reagents.

The oxo group (I.R. band at 6.01 μ) failed to react with NaBH_4 even under reflux condition. Rather a water soluble base was obtained during NaBH_4 treatment. But the starting material from the aqueous solution could be recovered unchanged by acidification of the alkaline solution followed by subsequent basification with ammonia. The failure of vomicine(II) to undergo reduction with NaBH_4 and its quarternisation on treatment with this reagent are explicable on the basis of the following resonance structures, of which (III) becomes predominant on treatment with sodium borohydride.

(I) C-Mavacurine

(II) Vomicine

(III) Vomicine

(IV) Haplocine

TABLE I

Chemical shift δ	Number of Protons	Splitting pattern	Probable assignments
1.65	One	Multiplet	$\begin{array}{c} \text{---C-CH-C=CH-} \\ \\ \text{H} \end{array}$
2.07	Three	Singlet	---N-CH_3
Ca.2.3	Two	Doublet	$\text{H}_3\text{C-N-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{---}$
2.4	One	Multiplet	$\begin{array}{c} \text{---C-C=CH-} \\ \\ \text{H} \end{array}$
2.62	Two	A pair of doublets	$\begin{array}{c} \text{---CH}_2\text{-C-N-} \\ \\ \text{O} \end{array}$
Ca.2.7	Two	Doublet	$\text{H}_3\text{C-N-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{---}$
2.9	Two	Doublet	$\begin{array}{c} \text{---C-CH}_2\text{-C} \\ \quad \\ \text{O} \quad \text{H} \end{array}$
3.2	Two	Singlet	$\text{H}_3\text{C-N-CH}_2\text{-C=C}$
4.08	One	Doublet	$\begin{array}{c} \text{---C-N-C} \\ \quad \\ \text{O} \quad \text{H} \end{array}$
4.2	One	Multiplet	$\begin{array}{c} \text{---C-O-CH}_2\text{---} \\ \\ \text{H} \end{array}$
4.45	Two	Doublet	$\text{---O-CH}_2\text{-CH=C}$
6.0	One	Triplet	$\text{---O-CH}_2\text{-CH=C}$
6.7-7.4 region	Three	Multiplets	Aromatic Protons
11.68	One	Singlet	Phenolic-OH

The NMR spectrum of the alkaloid (Table I) has been informative and can explain all the proton environments as expected from the structure II. The splitting pattern in the aromatic region is strikingly similar to that of haplocine, $C_{22}H_{28}O_3N_2$ (IV)¹⁰ and limaspermine¹¹ and the appearance of a proton signal at 11.868 which disappears on deuteration only on warming clearly indicates the presence of a strongly bonded hydroxyl group in the alkaloid which is in accord with the chemical data.

The identity of this alkaloid with vomicine was established from their undepressed mixed melting point determination, superimposable IR and NMR spectra. The mass spectrum of the alkaloid also provided the final verdict regarding its identity with vomicine¹². On electron impact in a mass spectrometer vomicine gave the molecular ion peak at M^+ 380, which underwent subsequent cleavage into several ion fragments (m/e 321, 160, 159 and 146).

It may be mentioned in this connection that LeMen *et al.*¹³ have recently observed the occurrence of vomicine in the leaves of *Strychnos nuxvomica* L. collected from Madagascar.

EXPERIMENTAL

The m.p.s. are uncorrected, the UV spectra were taken in a Carl-Zeiss Universal Spectrophotometer (Model VSU-1), the IR spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer Infra-red machine and the NMR spectra were taken in a Varian A-60 in $CDCl_3$ solution with $SiMe_4$ as internal reference.

Isolation of Vomicine

Air dried leaves (1.20 kg) of *S. nuxvomica* were exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in a Soxhlet apparatus. The petrol extract (5 lit) was concentrated, cooled and the thick oily extract was poured into 500 ml. of 5% aqueous acetic acid. The mass was vigorously agitated for 5 hrs and then left overnight. The gummy mass that separated out was filtered off. The aqueous acid fraction thus obtained was cooled, basified with ammonia and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed repeatedly with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, concentrated and chromatographed over neutral Brockmann alumina. On using benzene: ether (1:1) as eluent, a solid was obtained, which crystallised from methanol in stout needles having m.p. 271-73°j(dec.), yield 0.12 gm. It analysed for $C_{22}H_{24}N_2O_4$.

Spectra U.V. : λ_{max}^{EtOH} μ (log ϵ): 227 (4.29), 260 (4.03), 298 (3.64).

Spectra I.R. : bands at 3.10, 6.01, 6.18, 6.37 and 9 μ .

Attempted Acetylation

(a) *In cold* : The base (50 mg) was dissolved in 5 ml of pyridine. To this acetic anhydride (1 ml) was added. The solution was kept overnight and then poured into ice water, extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was washed with water and dried, concentrated and chromatographed over Brockmann alumina, when using benzene: ether (1:1) as eluent, the original compound was recovered almost quantitatively.

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(b) *Under mild condition:* The base (35 mg) was treated successively with pyridine (3 ml) and acetic anhydride (1 ml). The solution was heated in a water bath for 8 hrs. On completion of the reaction, the usual procedure for the isolation of alkaloid resulted in the recovery of the starting material.

(c) *Under drastic condition:* 70 mg of the substance was treated successively with pyridine (5.5 ml) and acetic anhydride (2 ml). The mixture was heated in an oil bath at a steady temperature of 150°C for 36 hrs. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was poured into crushed ice and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Excess chloroform was distilled off and the concentrated extract was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina using benzene: ether (1:1) as eluent. The eluates on evaporation yielded vomicine.

Gibbs Test: The substance (12 mg) dissolved in pyridine (3 ml). To this a solution of Gibbs reagent (20 mg) dissolved in pyridine (7 ml) was added. The mixture was diluted to 25 ml with sodium borate buffer when blue colouration was developed.

Sodium Borohydride Reduction of the Base: The alkaloid-A (100 mg) was dissolved in dry methanol (7 ml). The solution was allowed to cool and to it NaBH_4 (50 mg) was added portionwise. When the hydrogen ceased to evolve, it was refluxed for 48 hrs. The solvent was removed under vacuo and the residue left was taken in dilute acetic acid (10 mL) and filtered. The acid liquor was cooled in ice and basified with ammonia and extracted with ether and chloroform successively. The organic layer did not give any test for alkaloid with Dragendorff's reagent. However the aqueous layer gave positive test for alkaloid, thereby suggesting its quaternary nature. The aqueous solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid (pH 4.0), basified with ammonia on cooling and the base separated was taken in chloroform (4 x 50 ml.). The chloroform solution was worked up as usual. The chloroform residue yielded vomicine which showed no depression in mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of vomicine and their infrared spectra were superimposable.

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